

Rice Husk Ash Extraction with Organic Acid Leaching as the Pra-Treatment of Green Silica Production for Sustainable Industry Purpose

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Abstract:- Rice production in Indonesia has increased in the last 3 years. This condition resulted an increase in rice husk production as one of kind of its by-product. The high silica content encourages the potential of rice husk to become the raw material for green silica production. The utilization of rice husk to produce silica can shift the production of commercial silica (TEOS and LUDOX) due to the low cost of raw material, production costs, and of course- energy consumption. Treatments of different kind of organic acid ($C_4H_6O_6$ and CH_3COOH), variation of temperature ($28^\circ C$, $75^\circ C$) in duration of process (1h, 2h) in acid leaching was applied in this study. The parameters on this study are acid concentration and aging time on precipitation. The experimental result shows that the use of $C_4H_6O_6$ and CH_3COOH has been shown to reduce the levels of metal impurities, producing green-silica with 92.21% purity on the best silica product ($C_4H_6O_6, 28^\circ C, 2h$) with an amorphous phase of 61,26%, increasing surface area and pore volume of silica to reach $154,570 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $44,2513 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. The high silica yield was reached at 99,26%. The highest adsorption capacity of 756,4 mg/g, 824 mg/g, and 824 mg/g meet the quality standart of SNI no. 06-2477-1991 for silica product with good adsorption quality. The main analysis process using Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and Brunauer Emmet Teller-Surface Area Analyzer (BET-SAA). The obtained result suggest that applying organic acid leaching using $C_4H_6O_6$ can reduce impurities on silica product, producing mesopore-sized amorphous green silica with good adsorption qualities an an alternative hazardous to good material in the implementation of environmentally friendly chemical on micro-scale cleaner production.

Keywords:- Acetic acid, Green silica, Impurities, Organic acid leaching, Tartaric acid.

I. INTRODUCTION

There have been many studies state that rice husk ash contains a range of 88-95% silica content. With the combustion treatment, it was found that 94.95% silica content in rice husks was found⁴. In another study, it was shown that it was possible to isolate 93.67% of silica from rice husks [1].

The technique of extracting silica from its source in the form of rice husks can be carried out by various separation methods, such as hydrothermally, biologically,

chemically, and thermochemically⁶. In general, the silica separation process consists of removing inorganic compounds (metal impurities) K, Ca, Na, Al, Mg, and Mn, followed by the removal of organic compounds such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin contained in rice husks [2].

Rice husks treated with acid leaching produced the final silica purity of 92-93%. However, rice husk has a stiff texture, so in the acid leaching process, the acid solution is challenging to diffuse to the inner layer of the husk, and the operation process can only be carried out under certain conditions. In the study by Steven, S. et al., [3] it was shown that soaking rice husks requires operating conditions at a temperature of $200^\circ C$, a pressure of 6-8 bar, and vigorous stirring to break up rice husk particles and bring impurities out. While the structure of rice husk ash is more brittle, so the acid solution quickly diffuses, and acid leaching can be carried out at atmospheric pressure and low temperature⁹. Acid leaching carried out on rice husk ash produced silica purity up to 96.44% [3].

There is still metal impurity content which is one of the factors for the low purity of silica products [4]. The acid leaching treatment has attracted attention for its ability to remove mineral impurities and increase the purity of silica products [5]. However, the application of acid leaching is generally still using strong acids such as nitric acid (HNO_3), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), and hydrochloric acid (HCl) [6]. This inorganic acid is commonly used as a metal component remover during the silica production process [7]. However, the application of solid and hazardous chemicals can cause side effects on the human body and the environment in the long-term production design [8].

The characteristics of organic acids, which have low molecular weight, have potential as metal chelating agents. Tartaric acid ($C_4H_6O_6$) is an environmentally friendly organic acid [9]. $C_4H_6O_6$ not only functions as a precipitating agent but also as a metal chelating agent [10]. At the same time, acetic acid (CH_3COOH) is one type of organic acid that can form complex bonds with several metal ions [11]. Studies on carboxylic acid as a metal complexing agent with tartaric acid as a chelating agent are still minimal. Replacing the use of hazardous materials with less hazardous materials is the implementation of environmentally friendly chemistry in micro-scale cleaner production. Thus, this study was conducted to analyze the effectiveness of organic acids as environmentally friendly additives and is expected to be an alternative to dangerous strong acids in producing high purity low-impurity silica

from rice husk biomass. The experiment was conducted using the *acid leaching* treatment using 1 mol/L of tartaric acid ($C_4H_6O_6$) and 1 mol/L of carboxylic acid in the form of acetic acid (CH_3COOH). There are variations in temperature and duration of the acid leaching process, namely at conditions $T = 28^\circ C, 75^\circ C$, and $t=1$ and 2 hours. The best operating conditions for acid leaching to produce high-purity green silica products from rice husks have been studied. In addition, a thermal process is carried out ashing the raw material of rice husks in a muffle furnace under high-temperature conditions. Na_2SiO_3 was obtained from soaking rice husk ash (RHA) in 1 mol/L of alkaline NaOH solution. Green silica products were analyzed using SEM-EDX, XRD, and BET-SAA to determine green silica surface morphology, crystallinity level, and pore characteristics.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

A. Experimental Materials and Equipments

Materials involved in this research include fresh rice husks obtained from Penggilingan Padi dan Beras UD Maju Makmur, Trucuk, Klaten, Indonesia, were then washed and dried in an oven at $80^\circ C$ for 6-8 hours. The demineralized water was obtained from CV. Indrasari, Semarang, Indonesia, was used without further purification. 1 mol/L $C_4H_6O_6$ solution was prepared by dissolving 75.043 grams of $C_4H_6O_6$ per 500 mL of distilled water. 1 mol/L glacial CH_3COOH solution was obtained by diluting 60 mL concentrated CH_3COOH into 1000 mL of distilled water. 1 mol/L NaOH was obtained by dissolving 40 grams of NaOH per 1000 mL of distilled water. All chemicals used have a pro-analyst grade level.

The equipment used in this experiment includes oven (WTB 9010-0333 ED-56), muffle furnace (WISETHERM F-03), digital balance, mortar-pestle, glass beaker,

erlenmeyer, glass funnel, aluminium foil, hot plate, stirrer, pH indicator paper. The results of this study were analyzed using a Scanning Electron Microscope-Energy Dispersive X-Ray (SEM-EDX) JEOL JSM-6510LA, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) SHIMADZU XRD-7000 at UPT Laboratorium Terpadu, Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang, and Brunauer Emmet Teller-Surface Area Analyzer (BET-SAA) Quantrachrome Nova 1300E at UPT Laboratorium Terpadu UPN Veteran Yogyakarta. The location of the research was carried out at Laboratorium Dasar Teknik Kimia, Universitas Diponegoro.

B. Parameter, Variations and Experimental Procedures

The green silica is produced at several stages of the process. The first stage is the preparation of rice husk raw materials. Fresh rice husks are washed using running demineralized water to remove small particles such as gravel that are carried along with rice husks. Next, the rice husks were dried using a drying oven at $80^\circ C$ for 6-8 hours. The dried husks then entered the second stage, the calcination/ashing process, using a muffle furnace at a temperature of $700^\circ C$ for 2 hours. The calcination results in black rice husk ash referred to as Rice Husk Ash (RHA). The RHA particle size was reduced by using mortar-pestle. Some of the RHA entered the analysis stage as a control sample. The data on the characteristics of the raw materials were obtained. 10 grams of RHA were put into a beaker glass, then added 100 mL of 1 mol/L $C_4H_6O_6$ solution and stirrer to enter the acid leaching stage. The solution was then heated on a hot plate at $75^\circ C$ for 1 hour with a stirring speed of 500 rpm. Do the same for the acetic acid solution (CH_3COOH) and other variations in temperature and duration of the process. The variation of acid leaching temperature is $28^\circ C$ and $75^\circ C$ and the variation of acid leaching duration is 1 and 2 hours .

Fig. 1: Green Silica Production Process Flowchart [13] [14][15][16]

The RHA solution then entered the first filtration stage, where the acid solution was separated from the RHA residue with 10x10 cm fine filter paper. The dissolved residue was then rinsed with demineralized water at T=80°C. RHA enters the alkaline extraction stage by being contacted with 200 mL of 1 mol/L NaOH solution into a 500 mL erlenmeyer. The mixture was heated at 120°C for 2 hours with a stirring speed of 500 rpm. This is the process of forming sodium silicate (NaSiO₃). The solution then goes to filtration step 2 to separate the sodium silicate formed from the RHA. The following process is the precipitation of sodium silicate with an acid solution. 90 mL of NaSiO₃ solution was given 1 mol/L C₄H₆O₆ solution drop by drop until a clear precipitate was formed in silica hydrogel and stopped when pH=7. Test the acidity level of the sample with pH indicator paper. The silica gel was then rinsed with demineralized water at 80°C and then dried in an oven at 105°C for 6 hours. The flow of the green silica production process can be seen in Fig. 1., use mortar-pestle to reduce the silica particle size. The silica product is then weighed and ready to enter the product analysis stage. The silica product from this study was carried out in several stages of analysis. The morphology and shape of the surface of the silica particles were analyzed using the principle of atomic bombardment using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The percentage and identification of chemical compounds in the product were determined through an Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) analysis, and the crystallinity level of silica was analyzed by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) using data interpretation of Match!3, the volume of adsorption isotherms and specific surface area of silica particles were evaluated by the Brunauer Emmet Teller (BET) and Barret Joyner Halenda (BJH) method using the nitrogen gas adsorption principle, with the degassing process under vacuum at 280°C for 180 minutes. Data of characteristics pore can shown how the porosity quality of green silica. Porosity become the

important part to analys for some kind of adsorben product such silica.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Potential Uses of C₄H₆O₆ and CH₃COOH in Green silica Synthesis

Impurities chelating process has an essential role in the production of green silica. Organic acids are non- corrosive and more environmentally friendly. Acid leaching treatment with organic acids as chelating agents can reduce the levels of another elements than silicon, such as: Ca, Ni, K, Mn, Fe, and Zn [17]. From its toxic properties, the application of organic acids is more efficient because they have lower toxic properties compared to mineral acids such as hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, and nitric acid [18].

C₄H₆O₆ with the bond structure HOOC(CHOH)₂COOH not only as a precipitating agent but also as a chelating agent [16]. C₄H₆O₆ contains a carboxyl group and a hydroxyl group that can act as a binding agent for metal elements. C₄H₆O₆ can potentially reduce the levels of Cu²⁺ in the sample [8], chelating elements Fe²⁺ [9], and Fe³⁺ contained in water [19]. This is evident from the experimental results of acid leaching using C₄H₆O₆ at an operating temperature of 28°C for 2 hours can reduce Cu levels from 1,53% to 0,06% and Al from 1,02% to 0,16% thereby reducing the formation of CuO and Al₂O₃ compounds in green silica products (see Table 1.). The application of C₄H₆O₆ in acid leaching under these operating conditions has been shown to reduce the levels of several metal elements, which can automatically increase the percentage of green silica purity obtained, which reaches 92,21%, thus making the temperature of 28°C for 2 hours significantly the best condition of 1 mol/L solution of C₄H₆O₆ to increase the purity of green silica.

Compound	Chemical Components (% mass)								
	RHA	CH ₃ COOH				C ₄ H ₆ O ₆			
		(28,1)	(28,2)	(75,1)	(75,2)	(28,1)	(28,2)	(75,1)	(75,2)
Na ₂ O	2.04	1.04	0.90	0.61	0.26	23.05	0.54	0.95	0.45
MgO	1.43	0.01	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃	1.03	0.12	0.21	0.20	0.18	0.10	0.41	0.07	0.09
SiO ₂	51.84	62.19	89.49	89.41	84.02	52.56	92.21	81.25	60.11
P ₂ O ₅	0.08	-	0.08	0.04	-	-	-	-	-
K ₂ O	2.00	0.07	0.21	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.16	0.08
CaO	1.39	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.01	-	-	0.06	0.04
TiO ₂	1.10	-	0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-
CuO	1.91	0.79	0.41	0.97	-	0.97	0.33	0.23	0.83

Table 1: Chemical Composition Of Green Silica By Edx

The experimental results also show that the application of CH₃COOH in the acid leaching process at a temperature of 28°C for 2 hours can reduce Mg levels from 1.26% to 0.01% and Ca levels from 1.28% to 0.04%, thereby reducing the formation of MgO compounds and CaO in green silica products. In this operating condition, 1 mol/L CH₃COOH also increased silica purity by 72.62%, from 51.84% to 89.49%. CH₃COOH acts as a complexing agent that forms bonds with metal elements in RHA. This

is supported by the statement [20] where CH₃COOH belongs to the bidentate ligand group so that it can act as a complexing agent such as oxalic acid, ethanediol, and ethylenediamine. CH₃COOH has a carboxylic group (-COOH) which can act as a connecting ligand that can connect metal centers [21] to reduce metal impurities in silica, as well as with the characteristics of a relatively cheap and easy-to-obtain cost [11], making CH₃COOH

potential in optimizing the acid leaching process to improve the purity of green silica products.

B. The Role of Thermal Process in Affecting The Particles and Pores of Green Silica

Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) analysis was carried out to determine the chemical composition contained in the silica product. The high percentage of impurities is the cause of the low purity of the silica obtained 30. In previous studies, the data can be compared with silica synthesized using inorganic acids. Differences or deviations in the percentage of impurity levels can be caused by several things, such as the incomplete smelting process of volatile compounds during calcination, as well as acid leaching operating conditions that are difficult to stabilize, causing a decrease in silica content. The elements O and Si are present in the Si-O-Si and Si-OH groups contained in

silica. Detecting trace amounts of Cu, P, Ti, and Zn elements is possible from soil impurities in rice husks. Meanwhile, the presence of Na content was caused by the reaction of the formation of sodium silicate during the extraction process. Fig. 4. shows a photo of the surface morphology of the green silica product resulting from acid leaching with $C_4H_6O_6$ at $28^\circ C$ for 2 hours using SEM. With qualitative visualization, the silica material formed envelops the carbon, as shown in Fig. 4a). However, it is still clear that some carbon aggregates with a size large enough in the range of $2.6 \mu m$ were found. It was found that the particle non-uniformity in silica morphology was caused by the process of reducing particle size using manual milling and the possibility of forming aggregates in the product during drying process.

Fig. 2: Morphology By Sem Analysis Of: A) Rha, B) Control, C) The Best Silica ($C_4H_6O_6, 28^\circ C, 2h$), D) The Best Silica ($CH_3COOH, 28^\circ C, 2h$) From 1000x Magnification

Calcination plays a vital role in the carbon oxidation process. In this study, high levels of carbon were found in the green silica product, as evidenced by the detection of carbon in the surface morphology of the silica (see Fig. 1). This is presumably because the decomposition process of volatile materials does not run perfectly during calcination, causing oxidation to consume less carbon, so that the solids resulting from ashing still contain high levels of fixed carbon. This is probably one of the causes of the difficulty in achieving silica products with purity above 99%. Another cause is thought to be because the purity of silica in RHA in this study was only 51.84%, whereas, in other studies, the percentage of silica was found to be much larger (73.85%-82.80%) [22][23]. However, adding an acid leaching treatment helped to obtain low-impurity green silica with high pore volume characteristics, as shown in Table 2.

C. Crystallinity Ratio of Green Silica Product

The crystallinity index of the best silica product from the results of this study was calculated using the Segal method (see eq. 2), where the intensity value of the most substantial absorption spectra (I_t) became a function of the percentage of crystalline in the silica product (CI). $CI = I_t - I_a / I_t$ (expressed in %) where CI shows the crystallinity index of the green silica product (expressed in %), which was synthesized using $C_4H_6O_6$ at $28^\circ C$ for 2 hours, and I_t is the total intensity of the most substantial absorption peak. The results of XRD analysis showed that the strongest absorption peak of the best silica product was achieved at 869 counts. Substitute this value into equation to obtain a silica crystallinity index of 38.74%. This indicates that the best silica product from this study contains 61.26% amorphous silica. Based on the literature [24] the amorphous phase of silica is at $2\theta < 26^\circ$, for the quartz phase is at $2\theta = 26^\circ$, the tridymite stage is at $2\theta = 31^\circ$,

and the cristobalite phase is at $2\theta=33^\circ$. Silica calcined at a temperature range of 600-800°C has an amorphous phase. Calcination temperature that is too high is not the best

condition because under these conditions, tridymite will transform into cristobalite [25].

Acid	Ratio	
	CI (%)	Amorphous (%)
C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	38,74	61,26
CH ₃ COOH	72,82	27,18

Table 2: Chemical Composition Of Green Silica By Edx

The XRD results show that the green silica product has an amorphous phase, and cristobalite is supported by the results of the crystallinity calculation using the Segal method, as well as the surface morphology of the silica

product from 1000x magnification which shows an irregular silica structures. It indicates that the best silica product contain amorphous phase.

Fig. 3: Phase Profile By Xrd On The Best Green Silica

D. The Testing of Best Silica Product on Moisture Adsorption Process

The amount of mass of silica products and water molecules that can be adsorbed to the saturation limit is a function of the adsorption capacity of silica. Based on the data in Fig. 4, it shows that the highest water molecule adsorption capacity is obtained by silica synthesized with CH₃COOH at 28°C for 60 minutes, which is 825.6 mg/g, followed by silica synthesized by CH₃COOH at 28°C for 120 minutes at 824.4 mg/g which increased by 0.14%. The lowest moisture adsorption capacity was obtained from the control silica sample without acid leaching treatment, which was 395.2 mg/g [26]. The silica quality standard based on SNI No. 06-2477-1991 has a minimum silica absorption capacity of 750 mg/g. Therefore, four samples of green silica from the research meet the quality standards, which have adsorption capacities of 756.4 mg/g, 761,1 mg/g, 824.4 mg/g, and 825 mg/g, respectively.

Green silica is formed from siloxane (Si-O-Si) and silanol (Si-OH) [27] groups which act as active sites. The silica sample's active site begins in the thermal process at a temperature of 400°C. The active site synthesized with CH₃COOH at 28°C for 60 minutes worked well, as indicated by the high adsorption capacity of silica against water molecules. The acid leaching treatment increased the porosity of SiO₂ [28]. Data support that all silica treated with acid leaching had a moisture absorption capacity of 47.6%-78.78% higher than the control sample. This is because it has a high pore void space, thereby increasing the moisture adsorption capacity, and is supported by the results of the silica adsorption test on nitrogen gas which shows a pore volume value of 44.2513 cm³/g, where the higher the pore volume of a material, the higher pore volume of material will be the higher the adsorption power as expressed in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Moisture Adsorption Of Best Silica Product

Silica synthesized from rice husk ash without acid leaching treatment had a surface area of 116 m²/g with a pore volume of 0,23 cm³/g. The results of the BET-SAA analysis

showed that additional treatment with acid leaching (C₄H₆O₆, 28°C, 2h) increased the surface area and pore volume of green silica.

Method	Variables		
	Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cc/g)	Pore Diameter (Å)*
Adsorption	114,205	0,649	288,768
Desorption	242,20	0,736	126,279
BET	154,570	44,2513	-

Table 3: Saa Analysis Of Best Silica Product

Based on the literature, the amorphous silica product is of good quality if it has a specific surface area of more than 100 m²/g [29]. The data presented in Table 4. shows that the best green silica product (C₄H₆O₆,28°C,2h) belongs to the mesopore category with a pore size range between 2-50 nm and includes a product with good quality because it has a surface area of 154,570 m²/g with a pores volume of 44,2513 cm³/g, using the Brunauer Emmet Teller method so that in terms of pore characteristics, the silica product from this research has the potential to be used in industrial needs.

IV. CONCLUSION

A mesopore-sized green silica product with a purity of 92.21%, an amorphous phase of 61.219%, a pore volume of 44.2513 cm³/g, and a surface area of 154.570 m²/g was successfully synthesized from rice husk ash with organic acid leaching using C₄H₆O₆ at 28°C for 2 hours. This study concluded that C₄H₆O₆ could be an alternative to be applied in the organic acid leaching treatment to produce green silica with low impurities. There is no significant difference when compared to the use of strong inorganic acids. The absence of an organic acid leaching did not cause a complete RHA structural decomposition, so the mineral impurities were still trapped in the silica bonds during precipitation. C₄H₆O₆ has an excellent potential to chelate the levels of impurities to increase silica's porosity and adsorption ability. The green silica synthesis process using C₄H₆O₆ contributes to efforts to reduce the use of harmful inorganic acids that have long-term effects on the environment.

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